

IDENTITY CHANGE EXAMPLE ; CUKUROVA BOSNIANS

“175 Years of Social Change”

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Abstract

Cukurova Bosnians From 1840`s to Present.

“175 years of Social Evolution”

Nineteenth century to the present day, at different times of the Ottoman geography, has experienced migration for different reasons. My assessment is that interest groups on the social psychology of Cukurova Bosnians.

Looking out the window of social psychology, the Cukurova of Bosnian migration process, I found that a three-stage socio-ethnic ¹identities created fracture. the war between the years 1840-1920 and formed by the impact of social event ID, the second; The establishment of the Republic of Turkey starting and settlement originating from language and environmental problems in people who have migrated in the period up to the 1960 coup, the immigrant identity dealing with unemployment and despair, and finally in 1992 the Bosnian War in the "refugee " status falling Bosniak diaspora identity. I saw the effects of perception re-emerging identity built Bosnians in which adapts to the area already it.

The first two identity breakages were forgotten by the times. Cukurova Bosnians, while new home to fit naturally in the old identity and language, they also keep forgetting to their old native language and their culture. Bosnian War remind this forgotten retro-ID ². Culture, folklore and traditions and language revival was

¹ Greek is "ethnos" "public" is used to mean, here derived from the "ethnicity", ancestors of the common heritage characterized by that comes from a community of believers individuals / social groups represent (Kurubaş : 2008). Here the emphasis is sociological rather than biological origins. Greek said, expressing the unity based on kinship and tribal meaning "genos," which has a different meaning (Smith 1986). Assoc. Dr. Erol Kurubaş , “East West magazine, Ethnic Problems” Excerpt from article number 44 April 2008. Page 13.

² Retro-identity, old forgotten identity, vanishing smooth assimilation results in bio-genetic identification / perception is genos.

associations in order to re-learn, experience the culture and language in the western part of domestic Bosnian acquaintance and asked for help from relatives. This was the signal for a 175-year re-awakening of identity change.

The most interesting findings of my research, " Flower " is a Bosnian village. 3 family of grandchildren coming in here 1840`, " Bosnianoğulları " and that "they argue, but they did not know they came from the Bosniak and Bosnian language. I did 8 hours of video shots work in the area because I believe these findings should be protected for scientific purposes, I talked face to face with the witness of the event. I examine the information I learn in terms of social and psychological identity work. I decided to submit the results of the paper. This notification is made up of the true story that happened 175 years.

Keywords: *Perception of the Diaspora, Socio-ethnic, Retro-identity, Emigrant, Immigration, Refugee, Social change, Bosnian, Perception of identity, Social Psychological problems.*

1- Introduction

Bosnians migration process over time heavy difficulties and with traumas has passed . In this , both war , psychological the raid and environmental your terms as well as economic and cultural differences are also role has been . Immigration , miscellaneous but soon _ now same for reasons it 's homeland aspect seen to Turkey succession to be made why the one which one escape from the past distancing and safe being desire for vehicle dead is action .

Bosnian immigration (³), Ottoman in the hinterland citizen aspect where they are and today one by one state the one which 3 stages from geographies aspect realized ;

- 1- Ottoman period and Ottoman citizen / subject aspect arrivals
 - a) Official task , job and education purpose (1876` or until)
 - b) Compulsory as safe _ be purpose (after 1840s until 1920)
- 2- republican era arrivals (I. wave). More lots compulsory dead one process covers .
 - a) 1920 – 1940 Balkan wars and I. world war after ,
 - b) 1940 – 1965 II. world war and economic for reasons ,
- 3- 1992 Bosnian war and post- arrivals (IIth wave). Those in this group are in the Thrace region . opened refugee in their camps the rest of their relatives next settlers and

³Note: From Yugoslavia: During the violent movements of the Serbs who rebelled in 1804, those who fled the massacre against the Turks in the areas of Smederere immigrated to Rumelia and Bosnia-Herzegovina. With the start of the Ottoman-Russian War of 1806-1812, the Serbs, who received help from the Russians, increased the violence and pressure on the Turks even more. Meanwhile, the Turks who were able to escape settled in Manastir, Skopje and Kosovo. With the Akkerman treaty signed in 1826 , nearly 150 000 Turks were expelled from Serbia; About 15 000 Turks from Belgrade and other Turkish castles migrated to Anatolia and settled around the Sakarya river. Between 1908-1923, 300 000, between 1923-1933 108 179 Turks emigrated to Turkey. Migration movements continued after the regime change in Yugoslavia. In the years 1934-1960, 160 922 people settled in Turkey. Immigration from Yugoslavia continued in the following years until recently. Between 1960 and 1970 43 753 free immigrants came.

student aspect arrivals covers . BIH citizen who is a diaspora group being feature they carry .

Third in the group coming , more before from those who came different aspect Turkish they learned and themselves continually state aids made . Especially in the 2nd Term incoming Bosnian immigrants most problem attracting group has been . Serbian from the prints running away they come in the country (Ottoman and Turkey republic period) already seven on the front fighting and with famine struggle was doing .

Single assurances their souls in safety was that Buddha to them it was enough . therefore _ they come in the country come alive Start they worked , Anatolian salvation for to the fronts gone , martyr they are veteran they became Them Now They were the unique sons of Anatolia . Turkey of the republic substantive founder of the elements one they were the people . Minority never they did not (diaspora never they didn't) and themselves " intellectually Turkish from your heart They felt ' Bosnian ' .

2- The Struggle For Social Adaptation

Face seventy five your year accounting social psychological theories within emigration , emigration effects , social harmony , breaks , acceptances , individuals emotion , thought and to their behavior this your situations How reflected and results over i will stop Method aspect more lots observation based on and I'd like to send a message by e-mail one with talks i made reviews and to inferences I will stand meanwhile _ i made interviews with 7 hours of video recording I documented .

I interviewed individuals feeling and their behavior closely again again examination my opportunity it happened . in myself Bosnian one from family I do not come because from the ignorance remote , healthy one study to be for this I also archived the recordings . Moreover local from sources and I also took advantage of social media . Doctorate my field the one which social of psychology behavior , adaptation , migration , trauma , analysis I also used methods .

Çukurova in the 1840s to the sanjak (Adana at that time was an Ottoman vilayet) first came settled Bosnians internal migration with Konya's Ereğli from the town of Karaman from the province) 3 brothers with their families together they have come. where they settled Location dry and environmental aspect barren by working, because and soil working short in time wooded and they made it lush. Neighbor local villagers here flower like They called it " Flower " meaning. still in the village Its name is " flowery ".

of the flower at the entrance of the road on the left greet you right away one sign Caution attractive to fade, to fade face got caught one id cries. " Bosnakids " is a flour mill this signboard _ Village The headman, Mehmet Karakuş, said that they came from " Bosnian ". persistently while saying, the most (100 above) " utluk without mentioning " grandmother " can't stop. Bosnia none what they did n't see, Bosnian only word genius (Bosnian word except !) that they did not know, even that " utluk (blessed) grandmother " genius Bosnian that you don't know they said. Meeting my request lots old is and from his illness because they didn't want.

Utluk grandmother your past traces of to their grandchildren describing important one figure. mukhtar all what you know from him you heard said. from 1840 to the present this 1600 individuals of the village one to the population that you have reached with astonishment I learned. Now 30 households in the village Bosnian remains, the genes if Large to cities that they migrated they told.

Region to their village girl that they gave, Özcan (s) surnamed individuals Bosnian learned that they are I have been. nearby from Bosnians in about 8 villages your brides is village headman blackbird had told. In flower, from the past incoming migration your trauma no traces, if any lost Bosnian id like those memories disappeared. _ Villagers calm, peaceful (village to his funeral I joined) and increasingly hard working they seem.

all over the village arable armed with lands and wooded. here Bosnians Cukurova your cult they have assimilated. Cap and shalwar they are wearing. Dialects of Adana with they are talking.

3- Second Group And Trauma Traces

Second group and forced emigrate 1. wave aspect i will classify Bosnians more lots city to the culture they have . in villages those who live close to the city they are related . both in the village as well as city in the center houses and they have relatives .

this group Bosnian to your identity owners but with Adana culture integrated since they are Bosnian they didn't talk seen . Most 2nd or 3rd Generation They are Bosnians . More very outside of Adana Bosnians from Sivas Bosnians (Kolaşınlar) your identity that they live (in their home) and Bosnian good they talked seen .

However, Bosnians more smooth the one which and Like Yozgat , Kayseri from places again internal migration with incoming Bosnians there are . Ditto sivas Bosnians like these _ own between them and in their home more lots Starboard with his mouth they talk . their children if Bosnian more little they have learned . Reason if “ fork ” in the region tongue / snake language " perception is the prevalence .

Especially settled Turkmen-Yörük Turks Bosnian foreign tongue aspect from what they see , first come Immigrants also speak Turkish . because they don't know because they encountered other in the treatment Bosnian to children to be taught suppressed one behaviour has been . In time this perception Forgotten Teens _ Turkish good learned but this at once Bosnian they forgot . Turkish smooth to talk Bosnians social rapport in providing important role has received .

Bosnians on the one other in perception before with Albanians they are mixed . This is over time has been corrected . That 's why Some in places official in the records in the area Bosnians Although Albanian _ aspect only identity declaration been taken and to the records has passed . Payas Sokollu in the charter and in his castle incumbent Kale Dizdar and 73 soldiers wage records as “ Albanian ” pass () .

in this in Albanians to the local Bosnians with together to come active has been . Bosnian individuals more recessive because they behave Albanian id what's that out may be . in this group if role model Bosnian righteous is the master .

Salih Efendi, one of the Miyeviç and in 1876, before Mersin-tarsus (Adana Province to your starboard connected) and next to Cukurova came and made a difference with his entrepreneurship one is the figure . During this period Salih Effendi in the center

and two your brother's their families and in his factory with employees together in total one how much face Bosnian family is prediction are made . Prediction I say because official there are no records . More lots manners witnesses and of the living to what you said based on are information . for example Martinovic His family was in Salih Efendi 's flour factory . they worked .

period from 1876 to 1920 Turkey inside hard last one is the period . in Adana Armenian riots and The French took 4 years and 6 months . invasions , all citizens over heavy one trauma has created . Bosnians already in bosnia experienced rebel and wars results spouse timed trauma from what they've been through this in events second one trauma has been .

4- Some Regional Features

Bosnians relative marriage most little having crime _ rate low one is the people . Family to the older obedience is high . with their neighbors good they make a living . Girl kidnapping to the events they do not interfere and they don't miss . External marriages is too much . Innac as Sunni- Hanifi to your school they are included . Former from their culture remainder girl don't ask from the rituals Another evident one raid rituals there is no .

Unemployment rate is high . The reading rate is also high . daughters from men more is enterprising . Kitchen to the culture importance they give and Bosnian your meals now all is kept alive . There is quite a bit of “pita- burek ” in the region . popular one Bosnian is food . their coffee still shearing they say in the manner " from the side they drink 'with wheels ' .

Babine and podjedak / shijelo like cultural social relationships has been forgotten . These customs more They are also kept alive by many Istanbul and Izmir Bosnians . Folklore and national dress before was unknown but established after the 92 Bosnian war associations through Now youth wedding in associations folklore playing and national clothes they are wearing .

Gusle and accordion like music instruments even if it is known they have been forgotten . A lot former lovelinka , lullaby and folk songs from language say it

circulates but record under not taken (my in the video recordings I took there are some).

Moreover Caution attracting and research required one other on the subject of the Turks Halach on your arm including the one which With the Halaçoğulları same last name bearing the surname " Halac " Bosnians Presence is also important . Halaçoğulları living in Adana one Yoruk-Turkmen tribal .

5- On The Bosnia War And Perception Of Identity

Main themes of my work when determining social "Field Experiment " (4) , " Observation " applied in psychology and Interview (5) techniques , unstructured (spontaneous) interview technique (6) and qualitative (verbal) study (7) importance given .

Perception of the Srebrenica " Genocide " in the 1992 Bosnian War (this perception Turkey Bosnians owned), in Turkey ethnic aspect most close group the one which settled Bosnians emotion , thought and behaviours over negative loading making goalkeeper one effect has left .

Social in psychology " cognitive inconsistency " theory according to people action and his thoughts between mismatch , individual over negative to feelings path opens . Various ethnic groups genocide in their claims where they are nowadays , the ' group in the name of guilt ' and ' group in the name of resentment ' feelings origin and to the results models regarding both harm giving as well as damage seer by groups is considered (8).

this inconsistency psychology today in Turkey Bosnian lobby affects . The reflection of this is both in Bosnia. as well as in Turkey other Bosnian in individuals emotional

⁴"The most beautiful psychology is Social Psychology" Nuran Hortaçsu , İmge Ya. 2012 Ankara, p. 95

⁵ ibid , p.82/83

⁶ ibid , p.84

⁷ age , p. 79/80

⁸ age , p. 74

damage can give . This is international in relationships societies peace and before you damage aspect is also running .

This is the default group in the name of anger sense of and reflection also affected Adana Bosnians . forgotten and to disappear face haunted " ghost " your identity again spirit to find and to the revival why has been .

cultures between psychological buildings societies in communication active one element . Hofstede`s made to the studies USA , North Europe and Australia “ individualism ” in societies high.Europe's Balkans region , Asia , Africa and Middle East In other societies , “ Socialism ” was the feeling. more is high (⁹)(¹⁰). anyway belief and culture in the items similar features because you carry Bosnians and Turks are also socialist structure is dominant . this case Bosnians migration in their preferences why Turkey the ones you chose explains . your differences harmony it is difficult but to Turkey with immigration incoming Bosnians (all Balkan Muslims groups) easy rapport they were able to provide . Briefly this societies similar social view to the angles and to their beliefs they have.

6- Lobby Works And Setting Identity

the 1992 war starting group studies as a result Bosnian associations to be established started . like this social effect sources increase , you need individual as well as social social effect goals between I'd like to send a message by e-mail one interaction / communication to increase started .

Zimbardo and According to Leippe (1991) , ' Social Effect ' 3 different in the environment develops . in Turkey different in cities residence the one who Bosnian groups / individuals between persons _ between by communication starting social impact of the 92nd Bosnian war created by with momentum individual-group to your communication why has been . finally _ media and Press through Turkey`s other in their regions same social-psychological from the process with fellow countrymen relating to news Location to take had begun . like this I'd like to send a message by e-

⁹ age , p. 54

¹⁰N. Sakalli, 2013 p. 45

mail one , group and media (Zimbardo, 1991)` s why is widespread a " Social Impact
” Bosnian your identity in the formation effective has been (¹¹).

another _ substantive in the element social your influence at the ' target ' created
Bosniak in ' change ' effect (N.Sakallı , 2001) culture and your identity to settle why
has been.

7- Rapport

Şerif 's " Autokinetic " theory (1936) and Asch's " Lines experiment ” theory (1956),
real in life peoples other individuals ' fit ' and ' fit ' behavior what they exhibit showed
. This is because individuals inside where they are from society not to be excluded , to
be accepted and to be loved they want . migrate outside / different one from the ground
incoming immigrants , compliance about they show your behavior basis explains the
reason (¹²).

to Adana incoming bosniaks rapport process With this not left . of immigrants poor to
be less to power owner to be and themselves the one which their insecurities this
rapport behavior triggered . Other reasons if social _ psychologists ' social Need '
confirmation ' they say of the case is the effect . People one to society belonging be
they want and one group inside being motive it is strong .

People Moreover in knowledge reach , uncertain cases decision making and their
security providing their lives extension inside sleep they are in need . to information
based on social effect fit about lots important one Location keeps (¹³). like this Turkish
to speak they learned and Turkish they understand inside belonging be they want
Cukurova values about also have knowledge they have been . This is their rapport
process shortened and adaptation has provided .

Individuals trusted , connected they are from this new society what they learned
information abiding , Bosnian identity and values in terms of correct decision what

¹¹“Social Impacts Affect Who and How” Nuray Sakallı. Image. Ankara 2013, p. 15/19/20

¹²N. Sakallı, 2013, p. 37

¹³ N.Sakallı , 2013, p. 39

they received by thinking they relaxed (¹⁴) and Cukurova peoples inside acceptance they have been

Homeland lost , heavy traumas -lived Immigrants need to be ' loved ' will meet positive one environment in Çukurova of your siblings beside they found . Beyond on the side Some immigrant on your heels individual conduct exhibiting in immigrants Unfortunately identity depression and loss more fast could be.

Despite this the same in the neighborhoods and social in formations group Immigrants who were able to become (associated) if where they are to the environment rapport even if they provide substantive identities , values and their language they were able to protect . In Adana, this effect ' Easier ' also more is too much . from Yozgat in the arrivals relatively have been preserved . Pendik in Istanbul and Bayrampasa in the districts Bosnians still they are strong and their identity they protect . This is in Adana effect is weak . established two association , yet social identity , culture work , harmony , belonging etc on matters from studies lacks . drop-down Bosnian to courses demand increasingly less . Teferic 20 years of tradition before initiated formerly 'Pita' days aspect dedicated later if Bosnian culture lesson switch to ' Teferiç ' (¹⁵) made .

of associations role more lots touristy and cultural with excursions executive are made . without solidarity lots in conflicts why to be in terms of associationism about one unity and consensus yet could not be provided . Bosnian federation also 16 associations , federation outside is close to 60 society available . Personal and political interest accounts results Unfortunately wanted lobby effect platform can not be created .

8- What Can Be The Psychological Reason Of Migration?

To Jack Brehm's (1960) psychological theory of " Reactivity " according to any one persuasion don't to the attempt against (positive or negative), shown motivational one is the case . According to Brehm individuals to their freedom importance they give . In Bosnia, Serbian riots and nationalism currents when it started (in the 1800s) at the

¹⁴N. Sakalli, 2013, p.39

¹⁵ Teferiç means the same as ' Tepreç ' (to kick, to have fun) in Crimean Turks . The end of this tie should be explored . It is certain that Bosnians have connections with Caucasian nations. Musical instruments such as the accordion, the flute, and the sevdelinka melodies are also similar to ' Gusli ' .

beginning), inside serenity corrupted and Muslim elements (Turkish , Bosnian , Albanian , Pomak etc.) from the region migration to make must they have remained .

The same is true in the Balkan wars (1913-14) and cold battle post- crumbling of yugoslavia internal fight formed and independence for It has also been observed in the 1992 Bosnian war fought in the war . In short , individuals their freedom threatening under in individuals , psychological one reactive behaviour develops . Migration this reactive your behavior is the result .

by John B. Watson behaviorist to the theory According to Bosnians migration their behavior if we define This results get we can your migration flow scheme ; “ Natural stimulant effect War is unconditional stimulus if violence results formed trauma and unconditional The response is immigration . Moreover conditional stimulus if ethnic _ distinction and war ; conditional reaction again is migration ” (¹⁶).

Migration about conclusion aspect that I can say ; individuals freedoms threatening under when you stay individuals migration they (¹⁷). Moreover threatening below persons social effect to create to employees opposite resistance they show .

9- Bosnians Are Not A Minority

According to Moscovici (1985) , minority group subdued and rejected idea and behaviours representation the one who from people they occur (). Bosniak in Turkey immigrants / immigrants free and free aspect this in theory features they do not carry .

Bosnians , in together they live other with the peoples in their communication , feelings , thoughts and in their behavior almost one the sculptor statue he sculpted like Turkish with society one their brides to change afflicted , biological and sensuality they have influenced . Social psychology calls it ' Michellanj The effect is called '(¹⁸) .

¹⁶Paul Kleinman “Psycho101”, The Ocean. Istanbul 2014, 4th Edition, p. 72

¹⁷ N.Bearded age , p. 170

¹⁸Nevzat Tarhan “Psychology of Society”, Timaş ya. Istanbul 2014 7th Edition, p. 57

10- Social Problems

Poplin's (1978:4) definition by social problem, society or society constituent group and to institutions (Bosniaks and associations like) threat including one behaviour is the model (¹⁹). But Cukurova Bosnians i made studies , observation and but to my memory in the interviews will fit one threatening perception detection has not been done ..

Some hidden problems may be . This situation is specific conditions (birth rate , unemployment , language etc) a lot number of person by shared but group inside hidden remainder deviations is can show . fullar and to Myers (1941) every social problem is objective . a situation and subjective one from the definition they occur . about this healthy one analysis for Adana Bosnians about durable qualitative and quantitative data official aspect we have there is no .

Lens aspect hidden left conditions As a result , the Bosnian of the population birth rate of Bosnian talking about unemployment rate of negative discrimination etc like formed your situations all one by one as a social problem detection possible . This situation research not done . Reasons between social _ your problem subjectif aspect may occur threatening may detect .

Turkish in Çukurova citizen whether the region other speakers of their language (Arabic , Kurdish , Bosnian , Albanian) couple tongue / fork multilingual aspect they are stamped . In the early periods Bosnians settled down KöprükÖy district , as “ Gavurköy ” region its people by has been named . But this habit then leave _ has been .

West and According to Turner (2005) persons ' Halo ' effect constituent one approach there are . halo effect effective kneeless information status . Bosnians , Adanaya when they come local language they couldn't talk for local people on the first formed and next decisions over decisive They encountered the halo effect (²⁰) . first impact negative over time positive connotations and rapport when you start effect to positive returned . This effect if improvement If he didn't show , Bosnian-native in

¹⁹Nurşen Adak “Sociology of Social Problems”, Political Ya. Istanbul 2009, p. 18

²⁰prof. Dr. Demet Gürüz and Assoc. Dr. Ayşen Temel Eğinli “Interpersonal Communication”, Nobel Prize. 4th Edition Ankara 2014, p. 91/92

communication negative Contact could begin . Buddha bias and stereotypes why would be .

This is perceptual difference more Much of the Adana province between 1918 and 1922 . between French and 4 years 6 months occupation by Armenians by being formed traumatic one from the reaction originates from . Armenians Armenian speech and of the people don't understand reflection to the theory appropriate by the people of yore threatening aspect detected .

Bosnians Muslim their beliefs region in your people trustworthy and Easy going image has created . Briefly lens social your problem manifestation deviation , censure , gossip , prohibition as action (²¹) manifestation can . These effects are first generation Bosnians for valid even though i counted later from reasons due to acceptance and rapport provided .

Second and 3rd Generations this type with social problem is not encountered . Social in values your differences most member come down results social The problems have also decreased . However, Merton's By definition , positive functions with negative functions , harmony and integration will spoil in the structure from a yoke to a reducing ' dysfunctional ' social problem Bosniaks with local people between there is no can be said (²²).

to the work of William F. Ogburn (1950) based on fast social your changes why is the ' cultural of the delay path opened up social to voltage why will be one There was no social problem either . Bosnians fast social to change rapport they have provided . material culture in the elements occur incoming change , spiritual and ethic cultural behaviours and Ideas can be closely matched with .

Interaction of your approach view to the angle according to the region Bosnians socialization and society its members objective reality creation , joint your actions one product aspect visible (²³). partner actions tongue and gestures through they move .

²¹ N. Vow age , p. 21

²²N. Adak ibid , p. 26/27

²³N. Adak, p. 29

this meaning and in context physiological feature outside localized one Bosnian , my Bosnian unless you say to identify it is difficult .

Bosnians middle is income . first comers poverty they had taken . of poverty only Reason economic was not the same in time strength and income in the distribution imbalance , education level of low , qualified non- work power , politics apps , social your support absence , deprivation , historical , socio economic and cultural structure with poverty closely is related (²⁴).

first comers more lots arm -muscle strength requiring in the works they have worked . Business pitches more lots construction , plaster and tile work is on . their homes same in the neighborhood imece procedural they have done . Large and Large families if same courtyard inside only in rooms residence they were doing . These neighborhoods are; Kuruköprü , Yeşilevler , Flooring , Sinanpaşa and Köprüköy like from the center a little far they ate . Floor neighborhood to the center most close is place .

Death rate of to what is told by high school is period of first immigrants they live and all in the dormitory your troubles is is the period . deaths more lots plague , typhus , cholera , tuberculosis and from malaria was due . Medicine and vaccine insufficiency especially baby and old in their deaths increase showed . In almost every family baby to death it is found .

the 1960s next 2nd generation more comfortable one in the environment they lived . Reading rate increased and outside read and engineer and those who are doctors increase has been . Increasingly economic in cases to improvements found . selected professions between economics , business , doctor, pharmacist , architect and engineering is seen .

11- Family Structure

Bosnian in their families to the 1980s true Large family structure leave has been . Business find and married youth own their nests ability to establish to the strength owner they have been . Family heat violence now none not found . Relative marriage

²⁴N. Adak, p. 32

is minimal . from stranger girl take it don't give widespread , heterogeneous feature to disappear face it caught on .

with Albanians marriages and together legislative more chic is found one is the case . Child number increasingly is decreasing . Integration since it is provided one very very community same acceptable level _ level . Divorce action not approved . Bosnian female in marriages divorce rate more is too much . Girl their children to their families more lots they are connected . Old rate is too much . Extreme ends and politicize groups there is no .

Gans's (1962) urbanite and villagers describing work , immigrant of the population second and even in 3rd generation genius ethnic based relationships to continue well row , sitting with the district you identify with and thus your congregation borders with defined knowing local one feature it has won (²⁵) . In this context Bosnians before busy aspect they live from the neighborhoods by moving have expanded further we can say

Immigrants again poor in the neighborhoods they live . to Gans according to satellite in cities as well as in centers small villages shaped they live (²⁶) . like this in cities social problems to immigrants is reflected . These slums , poverty , education and health are problems .

to Durkheim by crime It is normal and functional . your crime is not one society unthinkable (İçli , 1993) . Bosnians between the crime to the definition entering behaviours happens . Water seller prevention in terms of Bosnians family structures and vineyards is strong . For this reason to crime mixing and crime at the rate is low .

12- Effects Of Children On Adaptation Roles

Cultural and intellectual development and rapport childhood during the periods starts and develops . by Jean Piaget kids over made social psychology studies to the results by to Bosnians generalization If we do , Bosnian of immigrants to their children they

²⁵N. Adak p. 193

²⁶N. Adak p. 193

apply behaviours and performative schematics results immigrant children into the new society more easy adapt they have been .

children genetic and cultural evolution as a result more knowledge at birth and of learning from your blessings to take advantage they begin . schematics of knowledge basis structure they are stones . Each schema one status (language , norms , values , ethics , customs , folklore etc.) to understand and him reply to give for used connected world symbols is the series . children this schematics by they learn and emotion , behavior and your thoughts they shape (²⁷).

the first generation of immigrants this schematics already they come society to the symbols by they are formed . But her skin generations , new region their schematics to learn they have to . therefore _ rapport in the process children's role it is big .

Bosnians assimilation and _ _ _ accommodation (fitting) first in their children occurs . tool for this those who if personally your parents it is itself . Or youth in generations own of your troubles to the same exposed stay with the threat against across they will be . Piagetin intellectual development he said the fact this adaptation will provide .

Cukurovada Bosnian families , children full Turkish and true let them learn saying In their own way sacrifice making family _ inside Bosnian they did not speak and kids own from their mother tongue deprived they have been left .

Albert Bandura social learning to the theory (1977), according to the Bosnian their children own cultural to your identity close symbolic in models they went away and environmental open to reinforcement they remained (²⁸).

children's role models , consisting of in space , TV and cinema the stars has filled . around them and in their schools Bosnian non- individuals also play a role with room to be they are candidates . This effect is 2 generations . Then The question of " who am I" in Bosnians more chic to be asked why has been.

13- Opinion Leader / Leader Problem

²⁷ Kleinman age , p. 123/124

²⁸ Kleinman age , p. 130

Cukurovada Bosniaks are from the first generation they got away and crossbreed one identity since they created because opinion deprived of their leaders they stayed . Today leader you are bored attracting groups at the beginning Bosnians is coming . Other available in regions (such as Izmir, Istanbul) of leaders existence , the area they don't know for sufficient is not coming .

in "Field Theory " like the Bosnians life fields increasingly is heterogeneous . Whereas individual and environment between perceived of tensions in the solution this domain and controlling the field of leaders role it is big . This is social of psychology basis conjecture the one which behavior of the individual with its features individual of your surroundings interaction results is thought (²⁹).

Group mind human opinion _ leader role _ model or from the leader devoid of when local to the administrations participation opportunity e - policy do not do that on the outside remains . 175 years Bosnian on Only one times Aegean Bagatur During the period (1970s) , the city council member of while Minister deputyship provincial general _ council member of Bosnian Fehmi afflicted there are . About 9 Bosniaks 3 ` from your village headman it is empty .

14- Characteristics/Contributions Of Bosnials From Adana

Orhan Kemal book from the characters one is “ Maho ”. Length two metre around the one which this Bosnian immigrant real one is the character . That's how tall long that a day rides engine start , the motor feet from among loss gone . Muslic from his ancestry the one which Maho from Adana Bosnians Nasreddin teacher like . Hair long the one which mahos same It is also famous for using a Harley Davidson style Engine . jokes with is famous .

of time even stone their bullies extractor this man boredom _ the one which all Bosnians came to his aid and they their rights defended . working in the factory women into a fight when ignited Noone could not separate , to Maho application when done room This with women by getting wet was able to separate .

²⁹ Kleinman age p. 158

His wife with fight the one who Maho his wife your house second from the floor down sixty (in 1982) poor woman at that time from there passing the one which awning bread car thanks to has been saved . Request Maho , am I angry? fearful one man.Muslicler busy one family whether estimated 70 households they are up to . From Sivas Dendil incoming muslicks They are also related to the Hochichs .

Author Orhan Kemal, from Muslicler Hayriye with the lady gets married . Bosnians closely O. Kemal , who knew them is affected and in your novels to them Location gives . like this Bosnians Literature in Adana contribute to the field found they become For example , " Mrs. farm"n in Jamshir from the 4 wives of the agha somebody he is Bosnian and her daughter Güllü in the novel is the protagonist .

O.Kemal Cemile place for your character gives in his novels . friend whistles , wanderer years , Strike , World house , Cemile like in his works protagonists Bosnians has been . coffee shop Aliş , Cemile , Gullu , Maho characters He is Bosnian . Tetka says to aunt and coffee shop Alişın Accordion and Gusli from ringing mentions . in his books to Bosnians this until Location giving Another one Turkish to the novelist you cannot find . All to Bosnians O.Kemalin this your novels to read I recommend . Most at least themselves one Another view in terms of have known they become

football when we say incoming from Adana Bosnian athletes if are as follows ; in the 1955/60s Bridge Sport and Ankara power Back playing Ramzi Hotlar (Adana sports-accident lead with death had done) , Zia Yurtlugil (Antalya sports) , Morlu Yaşar (Defense-Bridge) sports) , Recep Hotlar (Köprü sports-goalkeeper) .

Bosniaks in 1950 Bridge sport they set up . Bridge sports at that time amateur is a team . Adana's amateur Sport clubs ; Sümerbank , Milli Mensucat , Toros Spor , Seyhan sport's in their organizations in Bosnians contributions there are . Bosnians this They played ball in clubs . For example , Selim Nurgel Milli Mensucat (medium beck) nicknamed ' impassable ' middle fly . Moreover at once crazy / lightning group . _ many Bosnian Adana sports pro- because this Shack member has been .

in volleyball if ; National women's volleyball player howl Gülergin (Iskenderovic) , Ali Rıza Akin (Besiktas, DSI, now he is a coach) Horizon Akalın (A national trainer , SSK, TMO) Utku Süslü (DSİ; SSK, Petrol Ofisi) , Selin Akın 8 Çukurova Ü. ,

Bahcelievler college , Ankara Numune), Semih Akın (Halk Bank, İBB Yeniköy , DSI), Ramiz Zevker (DSI, Tokat , Hatay TEDAŞ) Cumali Years (Father Cumali - Galatasaray, Arçelik , Tuborg). rise Sasa in Yıldız , Adana DSI and slap in Niksar has played .

Horizon Akalin Sure Tara's is his grandson . Emin Tara gangbang made and one Serbian his pawn hit by for to Serbia input forbidden the one which is person . Sure aco (uncle) of the gang he is a paramedic same at the time .

in 1903 , Raonicka Buna) Raonik uprising This has been in the period to the Serbs against fighting / resisting families ; Mujchinovic in the New Market (Novi Pazar) brothers , Abid Alisanovic , Rusid and Sure is Tara (³⁰) . Serbs this resisting to families " Turkophiles " (Ottoman pro) name they have worn .

Swimming also in Adana name making our athletes there are . Senol and Hasbi Uçar (from podpećans) mother by They are Bosnian) brothers from the 80s swimming in the branch Bosnians madard they are proud . Hasbi flies This national coaching _ doing . Youth from generation to generation This national athlete in the ball the one which Simay Yavuz (Alibaşıç) is also proud what we heard between .

President aide the one which text in Uzbek He is from Adana . text Uzbek same in time Me too from primary school class my friend happens . a period Sample hospital chief physician making general Surgeon Atilla Akova is also Bosniak . terror in the events we lost Martyr police officer Adnan Can (Çurçeviç) with mercy we must remember.

15- What Is Diaspora Perception?

Bosnians have formed a diaspora for 4 different reasons (Turkey is excluded from this concept due to the Motherland and essential element approach). It is possible to list the reasons as follows;

³⁰Dr. Eyüp Musovic , "Ethnic formation and ethnic structure of the new Pazar population". September 2004 Alanya, p.87

1. II. Those who left before World War II (after the 1820 and 1840 Peloponnese revolts); USA, Australia, (Turkey), Arab countries.
2. The Bosnians, who were victims of the changing balances in the Balkans due to the defeat of the Germans; Australia, France, England, USA, Argentina, (Turkey).
3. Those who go to western countries for economic opportunities/finding a job/work. These are those whose connections with the homeland continue. They are not immigrants, but they constitute the most crowded group. They have the opportunity to act as a lobby.
4. Those who leave for political reasons are the most influential lobbyists. For example, Zülfikar Pasic , who went to France, opened a Bosnian Institute even here, carried out the most effective lobbying activities and introduced the Bosnian culture. The work of the institute is still continuing.

In 1922, the "Sancak" association was established in the USA, and Rifat Zecevic , the former politician and vice-president of the Swiss bureau of the SDA (Bosniak Party), was appointed . Esad Salihovic , from Yeni Pazar, became the head of the US branch of the SBMM (Sancak National Resistance Union) . Countries where they are concentrated; Germany, Switzerland, Austria, Sweden, Switzerland, USA, Canada, Australia, Turkey. This US-based organization defines all Bosniaks except BIH as “ Diaspoara ” for power formation .

Bosnians residing in Turkey and all associations (except Montenegro Associations) are against it. For Bosnians, Turkey is the "Motherland" . The idea that there is no diaspora in the motherland is stated as a common view. The word diaspora is not mentioned in any official record or declaration . Even if the Bosnian “Lobby” is mentioned, no work has been done as a lobby. It is accepted by Turkish Bosnians that the Bosnian students, who are BIH citizens, who come to study, operate as the Diaspora and Lobby of the “Young Bosnians Association”, which was established with the permission of the Turkish Grand National Assembly.

16- Bosnia Salih Efendi

In addition to 10,000 liras, he provided material and moral aid to the gangs who opposed the French and Armenian occupation of Adana. He gave Atatürk TL 10.000 to buy a plane. He is the man who made the Sabancı family rich. He is a valiant who loves his country and Adana. He is one of those who leave traces whose name should be written in gold letters.

Salih Bosnia Efendi, born in Mostar (Bosnia) in 1865, lost his father when he was 11 years old. When Bosnia left the Ottoman rule, the tense atmosphere in the Balkans led to war. When Bosnia was occupied by Hungary, they came to Turkey by ships from there. Salih Efendi, who first sailed to Alexandria and then Haifa , landed in Mersin port in Turkey, and was accompanied by his two brothers and mother.

Salih Efendi was almost fascinated by Adana. He bought hundreds of acres of land in the vicinity of Taşköprü, which is on the intersecting roads of the whole plain in Karşıyaka. The flour factory he established on the Seyhan river in 1902 is the first modern factory in Adana. Here he sold flour, opened a bakery and engaged in the transportation business.

When trachoma became widespread in Adana in the 1930s, Salih Bosnia established an eye examination polyclinic on Abidinpaşa Street in Adana. People were devastated by this disease. He opens a dispensary in Abidinpaşa where the Capar Pharmacy is located today. He brought ophthalmologists from Istanbul to have free examinations and distributed the drugs free of charge. It has contributed to the fight against trachoma in the city for years.

Picture: Flour Factory and Taşköprü

When trachoma became widespread in Adana in the 1930s, Salih Bosnia established an eye examination polyclinic on Abidinpaşa Street in Adana. People were devastated by this disease. He opens a dispensary in Abidinpaşa where the Capar Pharmacy is located today. He brought ophthalmologists from Istanbul to have free examinations and distributed the drugs free of charge. It has contributed to the fight against trachoma in the city for years.

Later, Salih Efendi, who opened an eye clinic in the Memleket (State) Hospital in Yüregir, also provided the financing for this place for years. He also made great contributions in bringing the first Turkish Pharmacy of Adana, Gülek Pharmacy, which was opened by Mustafa Gülek for the first time in 1902, to the city. Bosnian Salih Efendi was a person devoted to his homeland and nation, and he was extremely devoted and respectful to national and moral values. When Atatürk came to Adana, he hosted him in his factory with the people next to him and offered them treats.

In addition to the Bosnian Salih Efendi Mosque that he had built in his name, he also had two small mosques built. He was getting ready to build a school after the mosque he had built in Reşatbey , his sudden illness and subsequent death did not allow him to fulfill his wish. He established a foundation, and then its operation was given to the Foundations Administration.

He passed away on December 31, 1940 as a result of cerebral hemorrhage shortly after the fire of the flour factory. Salih Efendi, who had 3 marriages in his 75-year life and had 12 children, 7 girls and 5 boys, was also Bosnian. Micevic Salih Efendi, who came from his family, finished high school (today's high school).

Bosnian Salih Efendi had a land of 22 thousand decares. He owned yarn and cloth factories in Tarsus and flour and cotton gin factories in Adana. Bosnian Salih Efendi was founded in 1916 by Adana Ticaret . stock market headship made and Adana Farmers your union is one of the founders .

Adana was under occupation in 1918. He provided material and moral support to the gangs that opposed the French and Armenian occupation forces. Because he was in love with Adana. He was in love with his country. At that time, he gave Atatürk TL 10.000.- to buy a plane.

17- Grease Process After Trauma

Bosnian migrations are full of events that trigger trauma processes one after the other. During the 175-year Adana period, genocide was committed against Bosnians 11 times in the Balkans. Bosnians are a people who can't hold a stone. Minimizing the effects of trauma is possible by grieving. There is a basic rule in social psychology ; “Mourning should be kept where the loss occurred”⁽³¹⁾.

However, the Bosnians had immigrated, and they never had the opportunity to apply this rule. Rare people had the courage to go to their homeland with passports and find the opportunity to mourn. One of them is my wife's grandmother , Vasfiye Özgür (Memisovic). He came to his homeland in 1933 and was able to mourn his death in 1974.

We had the opportunity to observe the troubles of our elders who could not mourn properly. They lived until their death with feelings such as blood pressure problems, helplessness, depression, acceptance and effort to organize their life according to the new environment, the loss of desire but not being able to realize it.

³¹Ayten Zara “Psychological Problems as You Live and Ways to Cope”, Imge ya. Ankara 2011 p. 83

My inability to grieve has 3 consequences; first, developmental natural crises, second, situational crises that cause disruption of routine work, and finally complex crises and traumas . Trauma is a severe condition that results from factors such as violence, harassment, rape, war, terrorism, and causes physical, emotional, behavioral, cognitive reactions and post-traumatic stress disorder on the individual.

18- Conclusion

in Turkey , lobbying institutions and organizations, associations, NGOs, Businessmen, writers, media organizations, social entrepreneurs are the power of international public opinion for BIH.

Turkey from BIH for education and work after 1992, and the "Young Bosnians" association established by them with special permission from the Grand National Assembly of Turkey, and the members of the "World Bosniak Council" (based in the USA) have the potential to create a diaspora for BIH. The settled Bosniaks, who are Turkish citizens , have the potential to create public opinion as a lobby power.

Differences between Montenegrin Bosnians and Serbian Bosniaks and those coming from BIH are striking. However , they are all Bosniaks and the main thing is to work for the unity of BIH and Bosnia . There is a Bosniak community that lacks goals and leaders and has unity problems, and they are increasingly dividing.

The number of Bosniak associations is insufficient. There are nearly 60 associations. There are 16 associations in the federation. Due to the strict rules of the federation, unity of power cannot be achieved .

Bosnian leaders and opinion leaders do not act in a choir, unfortunately, they act as individuals who perform solo art. Young people are not paved. Unfortunately, Turkey's political diseases have spread to Bosnians .

The Bosnian lobby and political power are very weak. It is difficult to be aware of international studies. An invisible hand hides these works. For example, most associations are not even aware of the World Bosnian Congress .

Çukurova Bosnians are also an opportunity for BIH. It is especially the gateway to the Middle East and Asia . Adana is an important and strategic region on the old Silk Road. It is rich in terms of both food and business.

BIH Consulate should be opened in Adana . Adana is right in the middle of Mersin and Hatay Iskenderun ports. The Istanbul-Baghdad train route passes through Adana . The international TEM highway passes through Adana. The international airport is in Tarsus .

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